

CLIMAREST

D5.6 Open Call evaluation and results report

	Project number: 101093865	
	Project duration: 1 Dec 2022 – 30 Nov 2025	
	Project coordinator: Ida Beathe Øverjordet, SINTEF Ocean	
	Web site: www.climarest.eu	
	Deliverable ID: D5.6	Due month: M18
Title: D5.6 Open Call evaluation and results report		
Lead beneficiary: SO		
Prepared by: Thea Lurås Oftebro, Marta Pujol, Ida Beathe Øverjordet, Sigurd Hilmo Lundheim		

Abstract

This document includes the report on the outcome of the CLIMAREST Open Calls. The report was due in M12 but was delayed due to the challenges in selecting and contracting five replication projects.

To date, we have selected all five replication projects, and formally contracted five. Four of the replication projects have been actively engaged in replication activities, and one is starting early 2025.

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission services)	
CI	Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC)	

Deliverable type

R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, etc.	

Authorship information

Editor	Ida Beathe Øverjordet
Contributing partners	Thea Lurås Oftebro, Marta Pujol, Sigurd Hilmo Lundheim

Version history

Version number	Date	Description of changes
1	29.05.2024	First version submitted in the EU portal
2	05.12.2024	Revised report with updated results after Periodic project revision
3	13.03.2025	Revised report after contracting all five replication projects

Appendices:

1. Call text – PDF version
2. Call text – from the portal
3. Guide for applicants – from the portal
4. Frequently Asked Questions – from the portal
5. Application form – from the portal
6. Evaluation form – from the portal

Introduction

In July 2023, the CLIMAREST project launched a call for associated regions to participate in the project. The call documents are attached in appendix 1-5. The call aimed at finding 5 associated regions (replication sites with similar ecological challenges as the demonstration sites) that will be actively involved during the demonstration period (2024-2025) and after to showcase the feasibility of the solutions and prepare for implementation and scale up of the tested tools and technologies in their area.

The objective of the call was to facilitate the replication of demonstrated technologies and tools for marine restoration in associated regions in new projects after CLIMAREST is finished (2026-2030). Suitable associated regions are the ones that face similar challenges and needs for restoration and climate resilience measures as the demonstration areas. Third parties from the associated regions are expected to take part in the preparation of replication blueprints and business roadmaps for replication in their region based on the experiences in the CLIMAREST demonstration cases.

This deliverable summarizes the process of reviewing the proposals submitted to the Open Call as part of the CLIMAREST project. The report looks at the platform used for announcing and submission of the proposals, as well as the procedure to select candidates (reviewing the applications) implemented to date.

Funding box platform

FundingBox was the platform used for the Open Call. The platform had dedicated tools for managing the calls and evaluations (Figure 1). The application forms and evaluation forms are attached in appendices 5 and 6.

Figure 1. Platform dashboard for call management.

The calls can also be found online here:

First Open Call: <https://climarest-replication-site-oc.fundingbox.com/>

Second Open Call: <https://climarest-2nd-oc.fundingbox.com/>

Third Open Call: <https://climarest-3rd-oc.fundingbox.com/>

The process of reviewing the applications

This section will explore the different steps taken during the review process. The timeline for the Open Calls is shown in Figure 1. M1-M3 refers to the preparation phase of the call documents (not aligned with the months of the project itself). The calls were kept open for a minimum of two months (M4-M5). In M6-M7 the applications were evaluated in steps described below. M8-M9 is the formal process of contracting replication projects.

Open call timeline	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9
Call preparation	█								
Call open - 2 months				█					
Eligibility check						█			
Scope evaluation						█			
Experts evaluation							█		
Consensus group							█		
Consensus meeting								█	
Notification								█	
Formal checks and ethics								█	
Subgrant agreement (SGA) preparation									█
SGA signature									█

Figure 2 The timeline for the Open Calls

Eligibility check

During the first step of the review process, the applicants were assessed on the following criteria:

- Funding amount below 100 000 EUR
- Eligible activities (At least one)
 - Workshops/ meeting
 - Blueprints/roadmaps
 - Direct costs: Travel
 - Replication costs
- Costs calculated on costs actually incurred
- Local/regional authorities
 - Applicant
 - Participant
- Applicants from eligible countries and regions*
- EU member state / Overseas
- Submitted through Open Call tool
- Submitted before deadline
- English language
- Background check of the institutions (SINTEF system)**

* Countries that are not part of the CLIMAREST consortium and areas with similar ecosystems in neighbouring regions

** Background check includes check with RDC-database (Global Regulatory Information Database)(criminal records), country risk

Scope and expert evaluation

During the second step of the review process, each proposal was evaluated by the coordinator, one external and one internal expert appointed according to the specific characteristics of the applicants from the pool of External Experts. The external experts were independent from the applicants and were not Consortium partners' employees, permanent collaborators, or board members.

While reviewing the scope, the reviewers scored the proposals based on Excellence, impact and implementation.

- EXCELLENCE. Evaluate how the applicants propose to use the CLIMAREST restoration solutions in the respective replication areas.
- IMPACT. Analyse the overall expected impact of the upscaling of restoration measures in the given region in the short and long term.
- IMPLEMENTATION. Consider the application's description of plans for interaction with the CLIMAREST consortium, knowledge sharing and participation in the development of blueprints for upscaling of the suggested methods and technology. It also considered the likelihood of successful upscaling in the given region based on the elaboration on local barriers and mitigations given by the applicants.

Scope check

Each application was sent to the corresponding demonstration site leader to evaluate if the scope of the proposed project was in line with the work in the respective demonstration sites.

Evaluation in the FundingBox portal

In the portal, the evaluation form was set up with two scoring questions for each of the categories Excellence, Impact and Implementation, as well as a question about the budget. Each question had the option of adding comments. The evaluation form is shown in Appendix 6.

Consensus group and meetings

The consensus group was intended to consist of the demonstration site leaders, the coordinator and the external reviewers. We did not find the need for consensus meetings, as the external and internal reviews were aligned when it came to the quality of the applications submitted for each demo site in the two calls where we performed the evaluation. See below for details about each call.

Specific calls and outcomes

First Open Call – June – August 2023

CLIMAREST launched its 1st Open Call for replication projects on July 7th 2023, which initially remained open for two months. The deadline was extended once by two weeks, and the final deadline was on October 18th.

Eight applications were submitted within the extended deadline. Two of these applications were unfortunately not eligible due to the lack of inclusion of local/regional authorities or the funding criteria of the Horizon Europe program.

Six applications were evaluated by one internal and one external reviewer each. The results with the final scores and the scores for the impact section are presented in Table 1. The average scores for each project were calculated by summarizing the scores for Excellence, Impact and Implementation and dividing this number by the number of reviewers. In the case where the final scores were the same, the score of the impact section determined the ranking.

Table 1. Ranking of the applications to the 1st CLIMAREST Open Call for replication projects. The top three applications proceeded to sub-grant negotiations and will ultimately receive funding.

Rank	Institute	Country	Demo site and ecosysteme	Final Score	Impact score
1	Marine & Environmental Research (MER) Lab	Cyprus	Madeira, rocky bottom	14	
2	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece	Ireland, seagrass	14	
3	Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries	Croatia	Spain, softbed	13	8,5
4	Institute of Oceanography, HCMR	Greece	Spain, softbed	13	8
5	Archipelagos Institute of Marine Conservation	Greece	Ireland, seagrass	13	7,5
6	National Institute of Biology (NIB)	Slovenia	Madeira, rocky bottom	11	

CLIMAREST have five demonstration sites and aims to replicate solutions from all sites. In this round, we choose to fund three projects replicating the demo sites in Madeira (Rocky bottom), Ireland (Seagrass) and Spain (Softbed under aquaculture). Thus, the call was reopened for replication projects for the demo sites in Norway (Arctic fjords) and France (Oyster reefs).

Second Open Call – December 2023 – February 2024

CLIMAREST launched its second Open Call for replication site projects on December 8th, 2023. The final deadline was February 22, 2024. Two applications were submitted within the deadline.

The applications were evaluated, and the results showing the final scores are presented in Table 2. The average scores for each project were calculated by summing the scores for Excellence, Impact and Implementation, averaging over the number of reviewers.

Table 2: Ranking of the application to the 2nd CLIMAREST Open Call for Replication Site Projects. One project proceeded to sub-grant negotiations after this call.

Rank	Project	Project manager institution	Country	Demo site and ecosystem	Final Score
1	Oyster-Hives	Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)	Germany	France, Oyster reefs	13.5 Funded
2	SeDiMaR	Länsstyrelsen Västerbotten	Sweden	Arctic	7.5 Not funded

After the second Open Call, we had selected replication sites for the demos in Ireland, France, Spain and Madeira, and were still lacking one for the demo in Norway (Arctic). Based on these results, we reopened the call for replication of the solutions in our Arctic Demo.

Third Open Call – June – August 2024

The third Open Call was opened on June 25th, 2024, and remained open until September 12th, 2024, following an extension of two weeks from the original deadline in August. In this call, we specifically asked for an application for a replication of the Arctic solutions. Twelve proposals were initiated in the application portal, while only one was submitted. This application did, unfortunately, not pass the eligibility check and was not formally evaluated. The applicant was an NGO from the UK. The lack of eligible projects and the need for an arctic replication project led us to re-evaluate the runner-up from the second call after consulting the consortium and the EC.

Reevaluation of the Swedish replication project

Our attempt to select a replication project for the Arctic site through a third open call failed, as we did not have any eligible submitted applications after an extension of the deadline. Within the consortium, we suggested six different mitigation strategies, and after advice from the EC, we decided to proceed with negotiations with the second ranking project from the second call (Table 2), which was targeting replication of some of the solutions developed in the Arctic case. The applicant has now made the required adaptations to the project description (i.e. taking out practical monitoring and restoration efforts and focussing on the knowledge transfer, networking and blueprints of CLIMAREST solutions as required). With the required adaptations made, the Swedish replication project has now been approved and the contract is signed.

Contracting process

The contracting process was challenging but is now complete. Many of the challenges of the contracting process were caused by the need to include local/regional authorities. During calls #1 and #2, we announced that we accepted applications from consortia led by research institutions when they included local/regional authorities after having this approved by the EC. However, during the contracting process, it became apparent that the contract needed to be with the authority directly. We needed to redo our contract template, and the selected projects needed to redirect the contract negotiations to the authorities. In some cases, we were not able to contract the authority that was first involved in the proposal due to financial or legal obstacles on their end. We have also experienced delays due to the requirement of signing the contracts in the local language of the authority. However, despite all challenges, we have formally contracted all five replication projects, one from Croatia, one from Cyprus, one from Germany, one from Greece and one from Sweden.

Way forward

Despite delays in the contracting process, we have five formal contracts by March 2025. The four selected replication projects in Croatia, Cyprus, Germany and Greece have actively participated in the CLIMAREST activities, including regular meetings with WP4, in-person meetings (Brest and Malaga) and have been scoping plans for how they will work together with the demos in the final year of CLIMAREST. We expect that all the replication projects will have the opportunity to meet and discuss during the next consortium meeting in Croatia in May 2025. The development of the blueprints of solutions are initiated in December 2024 by individual meetings between the demo and replication pairs within WP5. These meetings take place monthly until the end of the project.

In summary, the process has been taking considerably longer and has been more complex than anticipated, but we have formally contracted five replication sites and will be able to deliver our collaborative deliverables within the project period.

Appendix 1: Call text – PDF version

CLIMAREST Open call

Background

The EU's 55,000km of coastline hosts over 40% of its population, and includes the Arctic and Atlantic Sea basin. In these areas, heterogeneous social settlements see marine and coastal environments strongly interconnected. However, these same areas and their ecosystems are also strongly affected by the twin crisis of climate change and biodiversity loss, affecting the resilience of coastal marine socio-ecological systems (SES). In this context, the UN General Assembly (UNGA) declared 2021-2030 the "Decade on Ecosystem Restoration" due to this widespread need to recover ecosystems that have been degraded, damaged, or destroyed by human actions. Given the urgency of the twin crisis and the fast approaching deadline of 2030 not only the Decade initiative, but also the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the Post-2020 biodiversity targets, there is an urgent need to develop and test new innovations in selected coastal ecosystems where restoration actions will secure the highest impact, to jointly come up with solutions for restoring marine and coastal ecosystems and increasing resilience of the SES.

About CLIMAREST

CLIMAREST is a HORIZON EUROPE project that runs from December 2022 until November 2025. It comprises 18 partners across 7 countries, and it's coordinated by SINTEF Ocean (Norway). CLIMAREST will explore the potential of restoration actions in five coastal areas (demonstration sites) on an Arctic-Atlantic scale, from Svalbard in the high Arctic to Madeira in the North Atlantic. The project will focus on five fragile and vulnerable habitats; seagrass meadows, Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas, shallow water rocky bottoms, oyster reefs, and soft bed benthic habitats. All connected by the coastal context in which they exist, their sensitivity to disturbance, and their general role as major drivers of habitat complexity and foundations of biodiversity in the ocean. Development, testing, evaluation, and presentation of a generalizable framework emerging from this work will provide a template for more efficient and effective restoration of degraded coastal habitats from the Arctic to the Atlantic.

CLIMAREST goals are:

- Develop transdisciplinary tools for ecosystem restoration and climate resilience improvements
- Evaluate the effectiveness of the tools in five ecosystems in the Arctic-Atlantic basin ranging from the high-Arctic Svalbard in the north to Madeira in the south.
- Examine the applicability of the tools for replication and upscaling on a basin scale.
- Ensure that the restoration and climate resilience tools is made available to users

Figure 1. Overview of the CLIMAREST demonstration areas

An action plan for the replication and scaling up of ecological restoration innovations developed in the demonstration sites will be drafted (Figure 1). Roadmaps and strategies to scale up restoration actions and improving the existing finance and funding structures will be created and applied to replication sites (associated regions selected within this call). Stakeholder from the replication sites will be engaged in this work through knowledge transfer during the demonstration process (2024–2025) and active planning of upscaling and replication of specific technologies in their regions.

Figure 2. Overview of the CLIMAREST project (Green box) in the context of the timeline of the EU Mission “Restore our ocean and waters by 2030. CLIMAREST belongs in the development and piloting phase (2023-2025). The projects funded in this call will participate in the preparation for replication and upscaling between 2026 and 2030.

Call for proposals

We are pleased to announce the launch of a call for associated regions¹ to participate in the CLIMAREST project. We are looking for 5 associated regions (replication sites) that will be actively involved during the demonstration period (2024-2025) and after to showcase the feasibility of the solutions and prepare for implementation and scale up of the tested tools and technologies in their area.

The objective of the call is to facilitate the replication of demonstrated technologies and tools for marine restoration in associated regions in new projects after CLIMAREST is finished (2026-2030). Suitable associated regions are the ones that face similar challenges and needs for restoration and climate resilience measures as the demonstration areas (Read more here: <https://climarest.eu/intro/>). Third parties from the associated regions are expected to take part in the preparation of replication blueprints and business roadmaps for replication in their region based on the experiences in the CLIMAREST demonstration cases.

WHO CAN APPLY

Eligible beneficiaries for this call are local and/or regional organizations from Member States², overseas and associated countries³ to the Horizon Europe Programme. Project lead by local and/or regional authorities will be prioritized, and in any case, projects must include a

¹ Associated regions are understood as “areas with similar ecosystems (e.g. neighbouring regions and/or regions in a different river basin) and/or less-developed regions, to build capacity to implement the innovative solutions..”

² Members States and OCT: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

³ Associated Countries https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-auratom_en.pdf

local/regional authority. We will aim to select one associate region as a replication site for each of the five habitats restored in the demonstration phase of the project (seagrass meadows, Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas, shallow water rocky bottoms, oyster reefs, and soft bed benthic habitats). Please note that countries that are part of the CLIMAREST consortium cannot receive funding: Denmark, France, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Spain.

Applicants should have a good command of English, must be eligible for participation in the EC Horizon Europe Framework Programme and must ensure the following obligations of the Grant Agreement⁴, namely Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality and security), 14 (ethics), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out action), 19 (information) and 20 (record-keeping).

The selected beneficiaries commit to carry out the following activities in their role as an associated region to the CLIMAREST project:

- Participation in workshops and meetings for knowledge transfer during CLIMAREST
- Participation in developing blueprints and business roadmaps for the replication sites.
- Pilot testing of the CLIMAREST restoration toolbox
- Interact with local stakeholders to identify restoration needs in the replication area

FUNDING & ELIGIBILITY

The grant each associated region can apply for is up to **€100.000**. Specified costs needed to be used to prepare for replication of given methods and technologies in the region as described above. Eligible direct costs: Travel to workshops and meetings, direct costs for hosting local workshops, information material.

Admissibility and Eligibility check

- Submission system. Proposals need to be submitted through the Open Call management tool [www.fundingbox.com]. Proposals submitted by any other means, will not be admitted.
- Deadline. Proposals need to be submitted before **September 8th 2023**. Applications must be submitted by the closing time and date of the open call. The time recorded by the FundingBox Platform, as submission time of the proposal, will be the official one. Late proposals will not be admitted.
- English-language. English is the official language for the open calls. The proposal must be in English in all its mandatory parts in order to be admitted.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/agr-contr/unit-mga_he_en.pdf

Additionally, proposals received will be checked against the Eligibility Check Criteria:

- Type of Activity and Scope
- Type of organization
- Established in an EU Member State, EU Overseas Countries and Territories or Associated Country other than consortium partner countries (as described in above)

The eligibility criteria are checked against the self-declarations included in the application form. Later on, during the evaluation process, the above criteria will be verified, and if an applicant is not compliant with any of them, the application will be excluded.

Evaluation

Each proposal will be evaluated by one independent and one internal expert appointed according to the specific characteristics of the applicants from the pool of External Experts. The external experts will be independent from the applicants and cannot be Consortium partners employees, permanent collaborators nor board members. External experts must ratify the Confidentiality Statement and the 'Non-conflict of interests' before starting the evaluations.

1. EXCELLENCE will evaluate how the applicants propose to use the CLIMAREST restoration solutions in the respective replication areas.
2. IMPACT will analyse the overall expected impact of the upscaling of restoration measures in the given region in short and long term.
3. IMPLEMENTATION will consider the applications description of plans for interaction with the CLIMAREST consortium, knowledge sharing and participation in the development of blueprints for upscaling of the suggested methods and technology. It will also consider the likelihood of successful upscaling in the given region based on the elaboration on local barriers and mitigations given by the applicants.

The consensus meeting will include the Third-Party Management Board (TPMB) of CLIMAREST and the independent experts who evaluated the proposals as well as the CLIMAREST ethics representative. The consensus meeting will decide on a list of third parties that will receive funding based on the ranking list from the evaluation.

Whilst normally the highest ranked proposals will be selected for funding, the TPMB might have fair reasons for objecting to a specific third-party project, like the alignment with CLIMAREST goals and scope, the ability to achieve the highest impact possible, as well as the existence of significant ethical concerns or a potential conflict of interest. In this case, the choice may pass to the next-ranked proposal. One proposal will be approved for restoration type. The European Commission must approve the list of projects receiving funding before the name and locality of the awarded applicants will be made publicly available through the CLIMAREST web site and the call platform.

APPLICATION PROCESS

Call opening: July 7th 2023

Call closing date: September 8th 2023

Single stage submission

Submission through the online platform at Funding box only

English language

Budget in EURO

TIMELINE

Evaluation and selection: September/October 2023

Granting completed: November 1st 2023

Project implementation: From December 1st 2023

Project end: November 30st 2025

PRIVACY

Personal data that will be collected, processed and published in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, also known as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

CONTACT

CLIMAREST admin team: climarest.eu@gmail.com

CLIMAREST Coordinator: Ida Beathe Øverjordet, SINTEF Ocean, Norway

Appendix 2: Call text – from the portal

CLIMAREST replication site application open call

Coastal restoration from the north to the south

The application deadline for CLIMAREST replication site application open call has passed.

BACKGROUND

The EU's 55,000km of coastline hosts over 40% of its population, and includes the Arctic and Atlantic Sea basin. In these areas, heterogeneous social settlements see marine and coastal environments strongly interconnected. However, these same areas and their ecosystems are also strongly affected by the twin crises of climate change and biodiversity loss, affecting the resilience of coastal marine socio-ecological systems (SES). In this context, the UN General Assembly (UNGA) declared 2021-2030 the "Decade on Ecosystem Restoration" due to this widespread need to recover ecosystems that have been degraded, damaged, or destroyed by human actions. Given the urgency of the twin crises and the fast-approaching deadline of 2030, with initiatives such as the Decade initiative, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the Post-2020 biodiversity targets, there is an urgent need to develop

CALL FOR PROPOSALS

We are pleased to announce the launch of a call for associated regions to participate in the CLIMAREST project. We are looking for five associated regions (replication sites) that will be actively involved during the demonstration period (2024-2025) and after to showcase the feasibility of the solutions and prepare for implementation and scale up of the tested tools and technologies in their area.

The objective of the call is to facilitate the replication of demonstrated technologies and tools for marine restoration in associated regions in new projects after CLIMAREST is finished (2026-2030). Suitable associated regions are the ones that face similar challenges and needs for restoration and climate-resilience measures as the demonstration areas (read more here: <https://climarest.eu/intro/>). Third parties from the associated regions are expected to take part in the preparation of replication blueprints and business roadmaps for replication in their region based on the experiences in the CLIMAREST demonstration cases.

Please see the Guide for Applicants for more information about the application process.

Guide for Applicants

ABOUT CLIMAREST

CLIMAREST is a HORIZON EUROPE project that runs from December 2022 until November 2025. It comprises 18 partners across 7 countries and is coordinated by SINTEF Ocean (Norway). CLIMAREST explores the potential of restoration actions in five coastal areas (demonstration sites) on an Arctic-Atlantic scale, from Svalbard in the high Arctic to Madeira in the North Atlantic. The project focuses on five fragile and vulnerable habitats: seagrass meadows, Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas, shallow water rocky bottoms, oyster reefs, and soft bed benthic habitats, all of which are connected by the coastal context in which they exist, their sensitivity to disturbance, and their general role as major drivers of habitat complexity and foundations of biodiversity in the ocean. Development, testing, evaluation, and presentation of a generalizable framework emerging from this work will provide a template for more efficient and effective restoration of degraded coastal habitats from the Arctic to the Atlantic.

CLIMAREST goals are:

ranging from the high-Arctic Svalbard in the north to Madeira in the south

- Examine the applicability of the tools for replication and upscaling on a basin scale
- Ensure that the restoration and climate resilience tools are made available to users.

An action plan for the replication and scaling up of ecological restoration innovations developed in the demonstration sites will be drafted (Figure 1). Roadmaps and strategies to scale up restoration actions and improve the existing finance and funding structures will be created and applied to replication sites (associated regions selected within this call). Stakeholders from the replication sites will be engaged in this work through knowledge transfer during the demonstration process (2024-2025) and active planning of upscaling and replication of specific technologies in their regions.

Figure 1. Overview of the CLIMAREST project (Green box) in the context of the timeline of the EU Mission "Restore our ocean and waters by 2030." CLIMAREST belongs in the development and piloting phase (2023-2025). The projects funded in this call will participate in the preparation for replication and upscaling between 2026 and 2030.

Appendix 3: Guide for applicants – from the portal

CLIMAREST

WHO CAN APPLY

Eligible beneficiaries for this call are local and/or regional organizations from Member States, overseas and associated countries to the Horizon Europe Programme. Projects lead by local and/or regional authorities will be prioritized, and in any case, projects must include a local/regional authority. We will aim to select one associate region as a replication site for each of the five habitats restored in the demonstration phase of the project (seagrass meadows, Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas, shallow water rocky bottoms, oyster reefs, and soft bed benthic habitats). Please note that countries that are part of the CLIMAREST consortium cannot receive funding: Denmark (Greenland is eligible), France, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Spain.

Applicants should have a good command of English, must be eligible for participation in the EC Horizon Europe Framework Programme and must ensure the following obligations of the Grant Agreement, namely Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality and security), 14 (ethics), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out action), 19 (information) and 20 (record-keeping).

The selected beneficiaries commit to carrying out the following activities in their role as an associated region to the CLIMAREST project:

- Participation in workshops and meetings for knowledge transfer during CLIMAREST
- Participation in developing blueprints and business roadmaps for the replication sites.

APPLICATION PROCESS

Call opening: July 7th 2023

Call closing date: September 18th 2023

Single stage submission

Submission through the online platform at Funding box only

English language

Budget in EURO

TIMELINE

Evaluation and selection: September/October 2023

Granting completed: November 1st 2023

Project implementation: From December 1st 2023

Project end: November 30st 2025

FUNDING & ELIGIBILITY

The grant each associated region can apply for is up to €100.000. Specified costs need to be used to prepare for the replication of given methods and technologies in the region as described above. Eligible direct costs: travel to workshops and meetings, direct costs for hosting local workshops, information material.

Admissibility and Eligibility check

- Submission system: Proposals need to be submitted through the Open Call management tool [www.fundingbox.com]. Proposals submitted by any other means, will not be admitted.
- Deadline: Proposals need to be submitted before September 8th 2023. Applications must be submitted by the closing time and date of the open call. The time recorded by the FundingBox Platform, as submission time of the proposal, will be the official one. Late proposals will not be admitted.
- English-language. English is the official language for the open calls. The proposal must be in English in all its mandatory parts in order to be admitted.

Additionally, proposals received will be checked against the Eligibility Check Criteria:

Country other than consortium partner countries (as described in above)

The eligibility criteria are checked against the self-declarations included in the application form. Later on, during the evaluation process, the above criteria will be verified, and if an applicant is not compliant with any of them, the application will be excluded.

Evaluation

Each proposal will be evaluated by one independent and one internal expert appointed according to the specific characteristics of the applicants from the pool of External Experts. The external experts will be independent from the applicants and cannot be Consortium partners employees, permanent collaborators nor board members. External experts must ratify the Confidentiality Statement and the 'Non-conflict of interests' before starting the evaluations.

1. EXCELLENCE will evaluate how the applicants propose to use the CLIMAREST restoration solutions in the respective replication areas.
2. IMPACT will analyze the overall expected impact of the upscaling of restoration measures in the given region in short and long term.
3. IMPLEMENTATION will consider the application's description of plans for interaction with the CLIMAREST consortium, knowledge-sharing and participation in the development of blueprints for upscaling of the suggested methods and technology. It will also consider the likelihood of successful upscaling in the given region based on the elaboration on local barriers and mitigations given by the applicants.

The consensus meeting will include the Third-Party Management Board (TPMB) of CLIMAREST and the independent experts who evaluated the proposals as well as the CLIMAREST ethics representative. The consensus meeting will decide on a list of third parties that will receive funding based on the ranking list from the evaluation. Whilst normally the highest ranked proposals will be selected for funding, the TPMB might have fair reasons for objecting to a specific third-party project, like the alignment with CLIMAREST goals and scope, the ability to achieve the highest impact possible, as well as the existence of significant ethical concerns or a potential conflict of interest. In this case, the choice may pass to the next-ranked proposal. One proposal will be approved per restoration type. The European Commission must approve the list of projects receiving funding before the name and locality of the awarded applicants will be made publicly available through the CLIMAREST web site and the call platform.

Please see the Guide for Applicants for more information about the application process.

PDF of open call

Personal data that will be collected, processed and published in accordance with Regulation(EU) 2016/679, also known as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

CONTACT

CLIMAREST admin team: climarest.eu@gmail.com

CLIMAREST Coordinator: Ida Beathe Øverjordet, SINTEF Ocean, Norway

Built with FundingBox Enterprise | [Legal](#) | [Manage your cookies](#)

Appendix 4: Frequently Asked Questions – from the portal

CLIMAREST

CLIMAREST FAQs for call

1. What type of organization is eligible?

Local or regional authorities of the replication areas need to be represented in the consortium and preferably lead the action. Partners can be research organizations, SMEs, or NGOs that are not based in CLIMAREST partner countries.

2. Can I submit my application if my organization is not yet established?

No, you cannot. To be eligible, your organization should be legally established in one of the territories mentioned in the Guide for Applicants, before you submit an application.

3. Who can apply?

Organizations established in an EU Member State, EU Overseas Countries and Territories or Associated Country. Applicants cannot be based in any of the countries of CLIMAREST consortium, which are Denmark, France, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Spain.

Applicants must be eligible for participation in the EC Horizon Europe Framework Programme and must ensure the following obligations of the [Grant Agreement](#), namely Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality and security), 14 (ethics), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out action), 19 (information) and 20 (record-keeping).

4. Can I apply together with other organizations?

5. How do I submit my application to the open call?

Applications to the Open Call must be submitted through the CLIMAREST Open Call microsite at [CLIMAREST replication site application open call \(fundingbox.com\)](https://climarest-replication-site-oc.fundingbox.com). Applications submitted by any other means will not be considered for funding (will be rejected). Inside the online application form there are specific fields to provide descriptions.

6. What happens if I do not submit my application within the deadline?

We do not accept applications after the deadline. We strongly encourage you not to wait until the last minute to submit your proposal. Failure of meeting the submission deadline for any reason, including extenuating circumstances, will result in the rejection of the proposal.

7. Can an entity submit two project ideas?

No, you cannot. In the case of more than one application being submitted from the same applicant, only the one submitted first will be considered and any others will be rejected. You can edit and update your initial application until the deadline - please do not start a new application.

8. Can I apply to more than one European Mission open call?

Applicants can apply for more than one open call. The two projects launching open calls in the Arctic and Atlantic sea basin under Mission Ocean will collaborate in the evaluation process, and it will not be possible to receive two grants for the same consortium.

9. What do we offer?

Under the CLIMAREST open call, the beneficiaries will take part in the project from 2024 to 2025. Beneficiaries are expected to:

- Participate in project activities such as workshops and meetings for knowledge transfer. For example, joining CLIMAREST consortium and WP meetings, as well as other communication activities and events.
- Interact with local stakeholders to identify restoration needs in the replication area and transfer this input to the CLIMAREST project.
- Contribute to the development of blueprints and business roadmaps for the replication sites
 - Test the toolbox and other innovations developed in the project, such as apps and protocols.

10. How should we estimate the budget?

Each project proposal will include a costs calculation in the Budget section of the application form. Checking the consistency between these costs and the expected work of the project will be part of the evaluation of proposals.

using HEU approved person month rates.

- Travel costs: Estimate cost for travels foreseen in the project including flights, accommodation and other related costs following the institutions regulations.
- Other direct costs (e.g. cost for hosting workshops, printing materials)
- Subcontracting (see below)
- Overheads (25% of sum of 1+2+3)
- Total costs (1+2+3+4+5)
 - Requested funding amount: Maximum amount 100 000 Euro. 70% funding rate applies for SMEs.

11. What costs are eligible?

Direct costs - specific costs directly linked to the performance of the project and which can therefore be directly booked to it.

- Personnel costs - daily rate of the staff of the beneficiary dedicated to actual work under the project (rounded up or down to the nearest half-day);
- Subcontracting costs; calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred, awarded using the beneficiary's usual purchasing practices — provided these ensure subcontracts with the best value for the money (or if appropriate the lowest price) and that there is no conflict of interest. Subcontracting is allowed for covering a limited part of the action (core activities cannot be subcontracted);
- Purchase costs - bought using the beneficiary's usual purchasing practices — provided these ensure purchases with the best value for the money (or, if appropriate, the lowest price) and that there is no conflict of interest;
- Travel, accommodation and subsistence;
- Other goods, works or services, if necessary to implement the project - for instance: consumables and supplies, promotion, dissemination, protection of results, translations, publications, cost related to IPR, if required under the Agreement.

Indirect Costs - costs incurred within the context of a project that cannot be attributed directly to the project, e.g. room rent, energy costs or general administration costs. A fixed flat rate of 25% of the eligible direct costs shall be applied.

12. What are the criteria to assess the proposals?

There will be 3 main criteria that will be considered by evaluators when assessing the proposals:

- EXCELLENCE will evaluate how the applicants propose to use the CLIMAREST restoration solutions in the respective replication areas.
- IMPACT will analyse the overall expected impact of the upscaling of restoration measures in the given region in short and long term.

likelihood of successful upscaling in the given region based on the elaboration on local barriers and mitigations given by the applicants.

13. How is the scoring system?

Each evaluator will score each criterion from 0 to 5 and will produce an Individual Evaluation Report. The final score per application will be calculated as the sum of the scores for each individual criterion. The threshold for individual criteria will be 3 out of 5 points. The total maximum score will be 15 points, with a minimum total threshold of 10 points.

14. Evaluation consensus group criteria

Once we have an initial ranking, ties (if any) will be solved using the following criteria in order of priority:

- Lead by a public authority
- The highest score in the Impact section
- Gender balance among the personnel responsible for carrying out the activities
- Other factors related to the objectives of the call to be determined by the Third-Party Management Board

After carrying out the Independent Individual Evaluation, experts who have evaluated the proposals will join in a Consensus Group, to agree on a common position, including comments and scores for all evaluated proposals. The Consensus Group will especially discuss the cases where there is a significant divergence between the evaluators' scoring. In case no consensus is reached between the evaluators, an additional evaluator will be included to provide an extra evaluation.

15. What will I get if my application is selected?

You will receive up to 100 000 Euro as a lump sum to cover the costs of developing the roadmaps and strategies to scale up restoration actions in the replication sites (associated regions selected within this call). You will also receive technical mentorship and support from the CLIMAREST consortium.

16. What type of support is available for preparing the proposal?

The '[Guide for Applicants](#)' is the main reference document. It provides detailed information about the requirements of the evaluation and selection process, and the financial support offered.

It is possible to contact the CLIMAREST admin team on email: climarest.eu@gmail.com. It is on hand to clear up any doubts you may have relating to the application process (eligibility rules, application form information requests, etc).

CLIMAREST replication site application open call

[FAQ](#)

[Guide for Applicants](#)

Built with [FundingBox Enterprise](#) | [Legal](#) | [Manage your cookies](#)

Appendix 5: Application form – from the portal

Form preview

This is how the form will render.

LEGAL AND CONTACT INFO

Organization's name *

Country *

Website (URL) *

Type of organization. *

- Research organization
- Non-profit organization
- Private company
- Local or regional authority
- Other

Local and/or regional authority in the consortium? *

- Yes
- No

Project leader *

Name and Surname

Email address *

Please enter only one valid email address.

PROJECT

Project Name *

Your project will be identified by this name

Replication habitat *

- seagrass meadows
- Arctic oligotrophic coastal areas
- shallow water rocky bottoms
- oyster reefs
- soft bed benthic habitats

Excellence and background *

Tell us about your project idea and background (max. 2500 characters).

Project implementation *

Tell us how you will implement the project (max. 2500 characters).

Impact of the project *

Describe the impact pathways of the project (max. 2500 characters).

Project partners *

Tell us about your project consortium (the name of the partners, the type of organizations, their role in the project and experiences in similar project) (max. 2500 characters).

Communication and dissemination *

Describe the communication and dissemination plan (max. 1500 characters).

BUDGET

BUDGET

BUDGET

BUDGET

1. Personnel costs *

2. Travel costs

3. Other direct cost

4. Overhead (25% of the sum of the three rows above) *Write not applicable if this field is not relevant for your application* *

5. Subcontracting

6. Total costs (sum of 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5) *

7. Total EU grant requested *

Personnel cost *

How was the personnel cost estimated? Person categories, person month cost per category, number of person months per category (max. 1000 characters).

Travel cost *

Please specify as detailed as possible how the travel budget is estimated (number of travels, flight cost, accommodation, other travel related costs. (max. 1000 characters).

Other direct costs *

How is the other direct cost estimated, what is included? (max. 1000 characters).

Overhead (up to 25% of the sum of the three rows above) *

How is the overhead estimated? Note that overhead is not eligible on subcontracting (max. 1000 characters).

Subcontracting *

Provide details about the foreseen subcontracting. (max. 1000 characters).

Appendix 6: Evaluation form – from the portal

External evaluation

This is how the form will render.

Excellence

Originality/novelty. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Solidity/robustness. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Impact

Potential for impact on research, society and trade and industry. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Plans for disseminating knowledge and for implementing research results. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Implementation

Project manager and project team. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Plans for carrying out and organising the project. *

- 5 Very good: The proposal addresses the criterion very well.
- 4 Good: The proposal addresses the criterion well. A few shortcomings are present.
- 3 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses.
- 2 Weak: The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
- 1 Poor: The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.

Comments

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).

Budget**The budget seems reasonable given the scope of work ***

- Yes
- No

Comments *

Please add your own comments here (maximum 500 characters).